

Visual Discomfort Scale English version

1. Do your eyes ever feel watery, red, sore, strained, tired, dry, gritty, or do you rub them a lot when viewing a striped pattern?
2. Do your eyes ever feel watery, red, sore, strained, tired, dry, or gritty after you have been reading a newspaper or magazine with clear print?
3. Do your eyes ever feel watery, red, sore, strained, tired, dry, or gritty when working under fluorescent lights?
4. How often do you get a headache when working under fluorescent lights?
5. Do you ever get a headache from reading a newspaper or magazine with clear print?
6. When reading, do you ever unintentionally re-read the same words in a line of text?
7. Do you have to use a pencil or your finger to keep from losing your place when reading a page of text in a novel or magazine?
8. When reading, do you ever unintentionally re-read the same line?
9. When reading, do you ever have to squint to keep the words on a page of clear text from going blurry or out of focus?
10. When reading, do the words on a page of clear text ever appear to fade into the background then reappear?
11. Do the letters on a page of clear text ever go blurry when you are reading?
12. Do the letters on a page ever appear as a double image when you are reading?
13. When reading, do the words on the page ever begin to move or float?
14. When reading, do you ever have difficulty keeping the words on the page of clear text in focus?
15. When you are reading a page that consists of black print on a white background, does the background ever appear to overtake the letters making them hard to read?
16. When reading black print on a white background, do you ever have to move the page around, or continually blink to avoid glare which seems to come from the background?
17. Do you ever have difficulty seeing more than one or two words on a line in focus?
18. Do you ever have difficulty reading the words on a page because they begin to flicker or shimmer?

19. When reading near fluorescent lights or in bright sunlight, does the glare from the bright white glossy pages cause you to continually move the page around so that you can see the words clearly?
20. Do you have to move your eyes around the page, or continually blink or rub your eyes to keep the text easy to see when you are reading?
21. Does the white background behind the text ever appear to move, flicker, or shimmer making the letters hard to read?
22. When reading, do the words or letters in the words ever appear to spread apart?
23. As a result of any of the above difficulties, do you find reading a slow task?

Option: No such experience (0)/ Occasionally (a few times a year) (1)/ Frequently (once every 2–3 weeks) (2)/ Almost every day (3)